

Cosmological Special Theory of Relativity

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Abstract: In the Cosmological Special Relativity Theory, we study Maxwell equations, electromagnetic wave equation and function.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Our article's aim is that we make cosmological special theory of relativity.

At first, Robertson-Walker metric is

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t) \left[\frac{dr^2}{1-kr^2} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

According to Λ CDM model, our universe's k is zero. In this time, if t_0 is cosmological time[6],

$$k = 0, t = t_0 \gg \Delta t, \Delta t \text{ is period of matter's motion} \quad (2)$$

Hence, the proper time is in cosmological time,

$$\begin{aligned} d\tau^2 &= dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0) [dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega^2] \\ &= dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0) [dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2] \\ &= dt^2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0) V^2 \right), \quad V^2 = \frac{dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2}{dt^2} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In this time,

$$d\bar{t} = dt, d\bar{x} = \Omega(t_0) dx, d\bar{y} = \Omega(t_0) dy, d\bar{z} = \Omega(t_0) dz \quad (4)$$

Cosmological special theory of relativity's coordinate transformations are

$$c\bar{t} = ct = \gamma \left(ct + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) \bar{x} \right) = \gamma \left(ct + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) x \right)$$

$$\bar{x} = x \Omega(t_0) = \gamma \left(\bar{x} + v_0 \Omega(t_0) \bar{t} \right) = \gamma \left(\Omega(t_0) x + v_0 \Omega(t_0) t \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{y} &= \Omega(t_0)y = \bar{y}' = \Omega(t_0)y', \\ \bar{z} &= \Omega(t_0)z = \bar{z}' = \Omega(t_0)z' \end{aligned}, \quad \gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_0^2}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0)} \tag{5}$$

Therefore, proper time is

$$\begin{aligned} d\tau^2 &= d\bar{t}^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} [d\bar{x}^2 + d\bar{y}^2 + d\bar{z}^2] \\ &= dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0) [dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2] \\ &= dt'^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0) [dx'^2 + dy'^2 + dz'^2] \\ &= d\bar{t}'^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} [d\bar{x}'^2 + d\bar{y}'^2 + d\bar{z}'^2] \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Hence, velocities are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} = V_x &= \frac{V_x + v_0}{1 + \frac{\Omega^2(t_0)}{c^2} V_x' v_0} \mathcal{N}_x' = \frac{dx'}{dt'} \\ \frac{dy}{dt} = V_y &= \frac{V_y'}{\gamma (1 + \frac{\Omega^2(t_0)}{c^2} V_x' v_0)} \mathcal{N}_y' = \frac{dy'}{dt'} \\ \frac{dz}{dt} = V_z &= \frac{V_z'}{\gamma (1 + \frac{\Omega^2(t_0)}{c^2} V_x' v_0)} \mathcal{N}_z' = \frac{dz'}{dt'} \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

In cosmological special theory of relativity(CSTR)'s differential operators are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{t}} &= \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} = \gamma \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} - \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{x}'} \right) \\ &= \gamma \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} - \frac{v_0}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right) \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{x}} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} = \gamma \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{x}'} - \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \right) \\ &= \gamma \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} - \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \right) \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{y}} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{y}'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial y'} \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{z}} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \bar{z}'} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)}, \gamma = 1/\sqrt{1 - \frac{v_0^2}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0)} \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Hence,

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \bar{t}^2} - \bar{\nabla}^2 = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} - \frac{1}{\Omega^2(t_0)} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right\}$$

$$= \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t'^2} - \frac{1}{\Omega^2(t_0)} \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x'} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial y'} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial z'} \right)^2 \right\} \quad (9)$$

The electric charge density ρ and the electric current density $\vec{j}$ are

$$j^\mu = \rho_0 \frac{dx^\mu}{d\tau}, j^0 = c\rho = c\gamma\rho_0, j^i = \vec{j} = \rho\vec{u}, i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (10)$$

In CSTR, transformations of the electric charge density and the electric current density are likely as coordinate transformations are

$$\begin{aligned} c\bar{\rho} &= c\rho = \gamma \left(c\bar{\rho} + \frac{V_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) \bar{j}_x \right) = \gamma \left(c\rho + \frac{V_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) j_x \right) \\ \bar{j}_x &= j_x \Omega(t_0) = \gamma \left(\bar{j}_x + v_0 \Omega(t_0) \bar{\rho} \right) = \gamma \left(\Omega(t_0) j_x + v_0 \Omega(t_0) \rho \right) \\ \bar{j}_y &= \Omega(t_0) j_y = \bar{j}_y', \quad \bar{j}_z = \Omega(t_0) j_z = \bar{j}_z', \quad \gamma = 1 / \sqrt{1 - \frac{V_0^2}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0)} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

2. ELECTRODYNAMICS IN CSTR

The electromagnetic potential A^μ is 4-vector potential. Hence, transformations of A^μ are

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\phi} &= \phi = \gamma \left(\bar{\phi} + \frac{V_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) \bar{A}_x \right) = \gamma \left(\phi + \frac{V_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) A_x \right) \\ \bar{A}_x &= A_x \Omega(t_0) = \gamma \left(\bar{A}_x + \frac{V_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) \bar{\phi} \right) = \gamma \left(\Omega(t_0) A_x + \frac{V_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) \phi \right) \\ \bar{A}_y &= \Omega(t_0) A_y = \bar{A}_y', \quad \bar{A}_z = \Omega(t_0) A_z = \bar{A}_z', \quad \gamma = 1 / \sqrt{1 - \frac{V_0^2}{c^2} \Omega^2(t_0)} \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

In CSTR, electric field $\vec{E}$ and magnetic field $\vec{B}$ have to satisfy Maxwell equations of special relativity theory. Hence, in CSRT, Maxwell equations are likely as special theory of relativity,

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = 4\pi\bar{\rho} \quad (13-i)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (13-ii)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \quad (13-iii)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} + \frac{4\pi}{c} \vec{j} \quad (13-iv)$$

In this time, Eq(13-i) is

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = 4\pi\bar{\rho} = 4\pi\rho \quad (14)$$

Hence, $\vec{E} = \vec{E} \Omega(t_0)$. According to special relativity, $\vec{B} = \vec{B} \Omega(t_0)$

Eq(13-ii) is

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} \Omega(t_0) = \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (15)$$

Eq(13-iii) is

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} \Omega(t_0) = \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \Omega(t_0) \quad (16)$$

Eq(13-iv) is

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} &= \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} \Omega(t_0) = \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} \\ &= \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} + \frac{4\pi}{c} \vec{j} = \Omega(t_0) \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} + \frac{4\pi}{c} \vec{j} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Hence, in CSTR, Maxwell equations are

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E} = 4\pi\rho \quad (18-i)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0 \quad (18-ii)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} = -\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \Omega(t_0) \quad (18-iii)$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} = \Omega(t_0) \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} + \frac{4\pi}{c} \vec{j} \right) \quad (18-iv)$$

Therefore, in CSTR, the electric field $\vec{E}$ and the magnetic field $\vec{B}$ are

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{E} &= \vec{E} \Omega(t_0) = \Omega(t_0) \left(-\vec{\nabla} \phi - \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{A}}{\partial t} \right) \\ &= -\Omega(t_0) \vec{\nabla} \phi - \Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{A}}{\partial t} = -\vec{\nabla} (\phi \Omega^2(t_0)) - \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{A}}{\partial t} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\vec{B} = \vec{B} \Omega(t_0) = \Omega(t_0) \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{A} = \Omega(t_0) \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{A} \quad (20)$$

3. ELECTROMAGNETIC WAVE IN CSTR

Electromagnetic wave equation is in CSTR,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E}) &= -\Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{B}}{\partial t^2} \\ &= \vec{\nabla} \times \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \right) = \vec{\nabla} \times \left(\frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B} \right), \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{j} = \vec{0} \\ &= \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \{ -\nabla^2 \vec{B} + \vec{\nabla} (\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B}) \} = -\frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \nabla^2 \vec{B} \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

Hence, electromagnetic wave equation is

$$\Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{B}}{\partial t^2} - \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \nabla^2 \vec{B} = \vec{0} \quad (22)$$

And,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{B}) &= \Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2}, \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{j}}{\partial t} = \vec{0} \\ &= \vec{\nabla} \times \left(\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \vec{B}}{\partial t} \right) = \vec{\nabla} \times \left(-\frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{E} \right) \\ &= -\frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \{ -\nabla^2 \vec{E} + \vec{\nabla} (\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{E}) \} = \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \nabla^2 \vec{E}, \vec{\nabla} (4\pi\rho) = \vec{0} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Hence, electromagnetic wave equation is

$$\Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2} - \frac{1}{\Omega(t_0)} \nabla^2 \vec{E} = \vec{0} \quad (24)$$

In CSTR, electromagnetic wave functions are

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{E} &= \vec{E}_0 \sin \Phi, \vec{B} = \vec{B}_0 \sin \Phi \\ \Phi &= \omega \left\{ \frac{t}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} - \frac{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}}{c} (kx + my + nz) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Where,

$$l^2 + m^2 + n^2 = 1 \quad (26)$$

According to Maxwell equations are in CSTR,[1]

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(t_0) \left\{ \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial t} + \frac{4\pi}{c} j_x \right\} &= \left(\frac{\partial B_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial B_y}{\partial z} \right), & \Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial B_x}{\partial t} &= \left(\frac{\partial E_y}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial y} \right) \\ \Omega(t_0) \left\{ \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial t} + \frac{4\pi}{c} j_y \right\} &= \left(\frac{\partial B_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial B_z}{\partial x} \right), & \Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial B_y}{\partial t} &= \left(\frac{\partial E_z}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z} \right) \\ \Omega(t_0) \left\{ \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial t} + \frac{4\pi}{c} j_z \right\} &= \left(\frac{\partial B_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial B_x}{\partial y} \right), & \Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial B_z}{\partial t} &= \left(\frac{\partial E_x}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial E_y}{\partial x} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Where,

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(t_0) \left\{ \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial t} + \frac{4\pi}{c} j_x \right\} &= \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \gamma (B_z + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) E_y) - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \gamma (B_y + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) E_z) \right\} \\ \Omega(t_0) \left\{ \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \gamma (E_y + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) B_z) + \frac{4\pi}{c} j_y \right\} &= \left\{ \frac{\partial B_x}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \gamma (B_z + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) E_y) \right\} \\ \Omega(t_0) \left\{ \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \gamma (E_z + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) B_y) + \frac{4\pi}{c} j_z \right\} &= \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \gamma (B_y + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) E_z) - \frac{\partial B_x}{\partial z} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Where,[1]

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial B_x}{\partial t} &= \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \gamma (E_y + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) B_z) - \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \gamma (E_z + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) B_y) \right\} \\ \Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \gamma (B_y + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) E_z) &= \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \gamma (E_z + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) B_y) - \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z} \right\} \\ \Omega(t_0) \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \gamma (B_z + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) E_y) &= \left\{ \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \gamma (E_y + \frac{v_0}{c} \Omega(t_0) B_z) \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Hence, in CSTR, transformations of electromagnetic field are

$$E_x = E_x', E_y = \gamma(E_y' + \frac{v_0}{c}\Omega(t_0)B_z'), E_z = \gamma(E_z' - \frac{v_0}{c}\Omega(t_0)B_y') \quad (30)$$

$$B_x = B_x', B_y = \gamma(B_y' - \frac{v_0}{c}\Omega(t_0)E_z'), B_z = \gamma(B_z' + \frac{v_0}{c}\Omega(t_0)E_y') \quad (31)$$

In CSTR, electromagnetic wave functions are

$$E_x' = E_{x0} \sin \Phi', E_y' = \gamma(E_{y0} - \frac{v_0}{c}\Omega(t_0)B_{z0}) \sin \Phi', E_z' = \gamma(E_{z0} + \frac{v_0}{c}\Omega(t_0)B_{y0}) \sin \Phi' \quad (32)$$

$$B_x' = B_{x0} \sin \Phi', B_y' = \gamma(B_{y0} + \frac{v_0}{c}\Omega(t_0)E_{z0}) \sin \Phi', B_z' = \gamma(B_{z0} - \frac{v_0}{c}\Omega(t_0)E_{y0}) \sin \Phi' \quad (33)$$

In this time,

$$\Phi' = \omega' \left\{ \frac{t'}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} - \frac{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}}{c} (l'x' + m'y' + n'z') \right\} \quad (34)$$

$$\Phi = \omega \left\{ \frac{t}{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}} - \frac{\sqrt{\Omega(t_0)}}{c} (lx + my + nz) \right\} \quad (35)$$

If we compare Eq(34) and Eq(35),

$$\omega' = \omega \gamma \left(1 - l \frac{v_0}{c}\right), l' = \frac{l - \frac{v_0}{c}}{1 - l \frac{v_0}{c}}, m' = \frac{m}{\gamma \left(1 - l \frac{v_0}{c}\right)}, n' = \frac{n}{\gamma \left(1 - l \frac{v_0}{c}\right)} \quad (36)$$

Where,

$$l'^2 + m'^2 + n'^2 = 1 \quad (37)$$

4. CONCLUSION

We know Maxwell equations, electromagnetic wave equations and functions in Cosmological Special Theory of Relativity.

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